

Book of Abstracts

Computational and Applied Physics Symposium 2025

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Computational Applied Physics Symposium 2025

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Preamble

On behalf of all the organizing committee members, FMSCS & FST faculties, and university staff, the conference chairs would to address their sincere thanks to the invited speakers, participants from all universities, and research institutions for their valuable and appreciated contributions to this scientific event in its first edition.

Many thanks are addressed to those who participate to the realization and the success of this event, and we apologize for any inadvertent omission, negligence, or execution delay.

With you, we aim to keep this scientific meeting a sustainable event for all scientists working on different topics related to the computational and applied physics.

Sincerely yours

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Plenary talks:

Pr. BOUAYED Nouredine (Univ. Blida 1), **“How quantum physics shapes our world?”**

Conference Topics:

Track	Oral Com.	Poster Com.	Total
<i>AI & Advanced Numerical Physics</i>	01	05	06
<i>Atomic & Quantum Physics and Applications</i>	03	07	10
<i>Computation and Characterization of Materials & Nanomaterials</i>	02	15	17
<i>Experimental & Educational Physics</i>	00	01	01
<i>Nuclear Physics, Radiations & Astrophysics</i>	04	07	11
<i>Optics, Lasers, Electromagnetics and Plasmas</i>	01	04	05
<i>Thermal and Energy Physics</i>	00	03	03
Total Participation	11	42	53

The CAPS2025 is supported by a national scientific committee with 64 members from 21 institutions (Universities and Research Centers).

The CAPS2025 was attended by 54 participants from 22 different institutions, including 1 plenary talk, 11 Oral communications (20%), and 42 Poster communications (80%), divided into seven major tracks.

The Attendance rate (effective participation / Accepted participation) was 85.7%.

Path integral treatment of a Dirac particle in a Kratzer potential (the spin symmetry case)

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In this work, the analytical solutions of the Dirac equation with the spin symmetry for the Kratzer potential have been investigated. The problem was approximately addressed using path integral formalism. We present the energy eigenvalues expression along with the upper and lower radial wave functions for any given k-state. The Schrödinger solutions for the Kratzer potential and Dirac's solutions for Coulomb potential have also been calculated and compared to results from previous investigations.

Keywords: : Kratzer potential, path integral, Green's function, spin symmetry, k, states.

*Speaker

Theoretical calculations of hyperfine structure constants for Ti II.

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Aims : Accurate hyperfine structure (HFS) constants for Ti II are crucial for reliable abundance analyses in astrophysical objects. This work aims to provide highly accurate and extensive theoretical HFS constants for key states in Ti II and to validate the accuracy of our theoretical models by comparison with existing experimental and semi-empirical data.

Methods : We employed both non-relativistic and relativistic methodologies to compute the HFS constants. The multiconfiguration Hartree-Fock (MCHF) method with the Breit-Pauli (BP) approximation (implemented in ATSP2k) and the fully relativistic multiconfiguration Dirac-Hartree-Fock (MCDHF) method with relativistic configuration interaction (RCI) (implemented in GRASP2K) were used. The quality of the wave functions-and thus the resulting HFS constants -was rigorously assessed by comparing the computed excitation energies with recommended data from the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST). We specifically present HFS constants for the $3d^2 4s 4 f 3/2, 5/2, 7/2, 9/2$ and $3d^2 4p 4 G^0 5/2, 7/2, 9/2, 11/2$ states of Ti II.

Results : High-quality wave functions were successfully generated for both the even ($3d^2 4s$) and odd ($3d^2 4p$) configuration systems. The accuracy of these wave functions, particularly their ability to capture crucial correlation effects, was confirmed by the excellent agreement between our calculated HFS constants and available experimental data for Ti II.

Conclusion : Our results show good agreement with experimental constants. Overall, the present theoretical hyperfine structure constants demonstrate better agreement with experiment than previous theoretical predictions.

Keywords: Hyperfine structure, Ti II, MCHF, MCDHF

*Speaker

Exact Pair Production in (1+2)D Using Dunkl Algebra and Bogoliubov Transformation

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We analyze scalar particle pair creation in (1+2)-dimensional spacetime under a Coulomb potential within the Dunkl formalism. By solving the Dunkl-Klein-Gordon equation exactly, we derive analytical solutions for both the angular and radial parts. Using the Bogoliubov transformation, we compute the pair creation probability and number density. The results show that particle production depends on the quantum number "m", the external field strength, and the Dunkl deformation parameter. Unlike the standard case, the Dunkl approach permits pair creation even for "m=0", highlighting the enhancing role of reflection symmetry in vacuum instability.

Keywords: Dunkl formalism, Dunkl, Klein, Gordon equation, particle creation

*Speaker

Prediction of relativistic ro-vibrational energy levels for a second Pöschl–Teller like potential via the Feynman approach

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In this work, the relativistic and non-relativistic rotational-vibrational energy equation is obtained by applying the Greene-Aldrich and Pekeris approximations to the centrifugal term and the Feynman approach to the Klein-Gordon equation with the second Pöschl–Teller like potential.

The energy spectra obtained are compared with those from analytical and numerical data. We have proven that the Pekeris approximation is better than the Greene-Aldrich approximation for calculating accurate relativistic rotational-vibrational energy spectra relative to numerical data for a second Pöschl–Teller like potential.

Keywords: Klein Gordon equation, Path integral approach, second Pöschl–Teller like potential, Radial propagator

*Speaker

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Non-relativistic Energy eigenvalues of Deng Fan plus a Ring-Shaped like potential by using SUSYQM approach

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In this article, we review the eigenvalues of the bound state energy of the Schrödinger equation with superposition potentials. Deng Fan plus a Ring-Shaped like potential by means of the SUSYQM approach. we use an improved approximation scheme to deal the centrifugal and the coulombic behavior terms. The bound state energy eigenvalues for the Non-central potential are obtained analytically.

Keywords: Schrödinger equation, Non central potentials, Deng Fan plus potential, Energy eigenvalues, SUSYQM approach.

*Speaker

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Three-Body Correlations in Single-Component Hydrodynamics

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Our earlier investigations emphasized the role of three-body correlations in single-component quantum systems, particularly within the context of ultra-cold physics. In this work, we extend that analysis by exploring how such correlations modify the hydrodynamic description and the corresponding equations of state, thereby influencing the behavior of collective modes. This approach allows us to develop a more comprehensive understanding of hydrodynamics in a single-component setting under the presence of three-body effects.

Keywords: three, body, ultra, cold physics, collective modes, hydrodynamics approach

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Charge Transfer Cross Sections in He + He Collisions A Quantum Approach

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We investigate charge transfer in the ion–atom collision system $\mathbf{He} + \mathbf{He} \rightarrow \mathbf{He} + \mathbf{He}$ within a quantum mechanical framework. The process is modeled by solving the radial Schrödinger equation using the Numerov algorithm over the energy range $10\text{--}10^1$ Hartree, based on the diabatic potentials of Loreau *et al.*. The computed phase shifts provide access to both elastic and charge transfer cross sections. The results shed light on fundamental mechanisms in ion–atom interactions with potential applications in plasma physics and hydrogen-related technologies, particularly impurity management and helium separation.

Keywords: Potential energy curves, Numerical simulation, Charge transfer, Elastic scattering, Green hydrogen

*Speaker

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Prediction of the Molar Entropy of Chlorine and Iodine Molecules Using the Feynman Method

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In this work, analytical expressions of the molar entropy for the ground states of Chlorine and Iodine gases were derived. To do this, explicit expression of the energy spectrum for the q -deformed hyperbolic Scarf II potential was obtained using the Feynman path integrals formalism. Using the energy spectrum and the Poisson summation formula, the explicit expression of the partition function was derived. Using this last, we derive explicit expressions of the molar entropy of (Cl₂) and (I₂) molecules. The results are in very good agreement compared to the experimental data from the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST).

Keywords: Path integrals, partition function, molar entropy

*Speaker

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Five Fold differential cross sections (5DCS) for the electron impact double ionization of N.

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Collisions between charged and neutral particles are central to atomic and molecular physics. Among these, electron-impact ionization of atomic and molecular targets remains a key topic of investigation. Of particular interest is double ionization, in which an incident electron collides with a target and causes the simultaneous ejection of two bound electrons. When these two electrons are detected in coincidence with the scattered projectile, the reaction is denoted (e,3e).

The nitrogen molecule (N) is of special importance because of its role in biological materials such as proteins and DNA. Understanding the mechanisms of its double ionization through the (e,3e) process is therefore relevant both to fundamental collision physics and to assessing electron-induced effects in biological systems.

In this work, we present five-fold differential cross-section (5DCS) calculations for the (e,3e) double ionization of the outermost molecular orbital of N at an intermediate incident energy of about 600 eV. The calculations employ the 2CWG model, where the two ejected electrons are described by Coulomb wave functions with a Gamow factor in the final state. The initial state is represented by a single-center wave function derived from the self-consistent-field Hartree-Fock method using the linear-combination-of-atomic-orbitals molecular-orbital (LCAO-MO) approximation (1).

Our results are compared with the experimental measurements of Li *et al.* (2) and with previous theoretical predictions based on the two-center continuum wavefunction with correlation (TCC-C) model (3).

Keywords: Cross section, Ionization, Electron impact.

*Speaker

Self-Bound Quantum Droplet-GUP

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This research investigates the quantum gravity effects on self-bound quantum droplet of one-dimensional Bose-Bose mixtures. These quantum states are stabilized owing to the delicate competition between attractive mean-field interaction (corresponding to a negative vacuum pressure) and repulsive beyond mean-field quantum fluctuations (corresponding to a positive vacuum pressure) originating from the Lee-Huang-Yang (LHY) correction. Our study focuses on the two types of quantum droplet, small droplets of an approximately Gaussian shape and large "puddles" with a prominent flat-top plateau. We analyze this within the framework of mean-field theory, incorporating both Lee-Huang-Yang (LHY) corrections and GUP corrections. We solved variationally the underlying generalized Gross-Pitaevskii equation which includes the effects of quadratic and cubic nonlinearities, based on the Super-Gaussian ansatz. This work aims to develop the associated generalized uncertainty principle to the self bound droplet and its minimum length. Our finding suggest considerably improved bounds of GUP parameters and provide insights into the reconciliation of gravity with quantum mechanics in current experimental setups. Moreover, it explores the potential of quantum droplets as a platform for testing quantum gravity.

Keywords: Quantum droplet, Quantum Gravity, GUP, SuperGaussian ansatz, minimum length

*Speaker

A Review of Raman Spectroscopy Applications in Nuclear Forensic Analysis

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1

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Nuclear forensics plays a crucial role in national and international security efforts aimed at identifying, tracing, and characterizing radioactive materials found outside regulatory control. As the field evolves, there has been increasing emphasis on developing non-destructive, high-resolution analytical techniques that can provide structural, chemical, and morphological signatures essential for source attribution and reconstructing process history. Among these, Raman spectroscopy has emerged as a powerful and useful tool for the forensic analysis of nuclear materials. Its ability to offer molecular-level information with minimal sample preparation, combined with remote sensing capabilities and compatibility with radioactive environments, makes it particularly suited for the analysis of uranium ore concentrates (UOCs), actinide oxides, and post-detonation residues. Recent advances in micro-Raman and surface-enhanced Raman techniques have enabled the detection and classification of uranic compounds at the individual particle level, even in complex or trace-laden matrices such as aerosols. This review explores the growing role of Raman spectroscopy in nuclear forensics, its methodological advantages and limitations, and its complementary value alongside established techniques such as X-ray diffraction (XRD) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Indeed, the state-of-the-art applications of Raman spectroscopy for the characterization of UOCs, uranium oxides (UO₂, U₃O₈), plutonium dioxide (PuO₂), and mixed oxide (MOX) fuels are reviewed and synthesized from the existing literature.

Keywords: Nuclear forensics, Raman spectroscopy, Uranium ore concentrate (UOC), Non, destructive analysis, uranium oxides, plutonium dioxide.

*Speaker

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Phenomenology of the Conformal Two-Higgs-Doublet Model

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Abstract

In this work, we investigate the viability and potential predictions of the so-called scale-invariant two-Higgs-doublet model (SI-2HDM). As the quadratic terms are absent, the electroweak symmetry breaking (EWSB) is triggered by quantum corrections, leading to a more constrained parameter space compared to the minimal two-Higgs-doublet model (2HDM). After renormalizing the scalar sector and imposing relevant theoretical and experimental constraints such as perturbativity, vacuum stability, perturbative unitarity, electroweak precision tests, BSM Higgs decays, and the LEP constraints, we demonstrate that collider experiments can provide interesting predictions, where the SI-2HDM predicts substantial suppression in the di-Higgs production cross section at LHC@13TeV, by up to 45.5% compared to the Standard Model prediction.

Keywords: Standard Model, scale, invariant two, Higgs, doublet model, di, Higgs production cross section, LHC

*Speaker

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Natural Quartz-Based Dosimetry

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Quartz, naturally found in various geological materials like rock, sand and sediments, has garnered significant attention in the passive dosimetry field due to its unique optoelectronic properties, crystalline structure rich in defects acting as a natural trap for charge carriers generated by ionizing radiation, widespread availability, chemical stability, and long storage stability over timescales. These characteristics make natural quartz an invaluable material for a diverse range of dosimetric applications, from retrospective accident dosimetry and environmental monitoring to archeological dating and geological provenance studies (1-3). In the present study, the soil samples were collected from southern Algeria. The separation of pure quartz was ensured using well-defined chemical processes. Its elemental composition was studied by XRF analysis, showing 86.58 % SiO₂ elemental weight percent. The as-extracted sample was then subjected to a thermal treatment to study the influence of temperature on the response of natural quartz. Thermoluminescence (TL) and Optically Stimulated Luminescence (CW-OSL) measurements were carried out using Risø TL-OSL reader DA-20 model with two optical sources (Blue and IR-Leds) and a constant heating rate of 5°C/s from room temperature to 450°C. Beta dose response of the extracted quartz was investigated in the dose range of 0.1-20 Gy for both cases, TL and OSL, revealing a good linearity within the considered region. Kinetic parameters were also discussed using TGCD and Origin, demonstrating the presence of three TL peaks for the 1000°C treated sample with activation energies varying from 0.30 eV to 0.95 eV. The photoionization cross-sections were estimated to vary between and for deconvolution of decay curve into 3 components basing on general order model for the CW-OSL. In this context, the extraction methodology has demonstrated effectiveness. The MDD test is required to allow its useful application in retrospective dosimetry.

Keywords: TL, OSL, Quartz, Deconvolution.

*Speaker

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Scalarized gravastars and its astrophysical implications

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Gravastars (gravitational vacuum stars) have been proposed as theoretical alternatives to black holes, characterized by an internal de Sitter core, a thin shell of ultra-stiff matter, and an exterior Schwarzschild solution. In this work, we investigate scalarized gravastars coupled to scalar field, particularly within scalar-tensor theories of gravity, exhibiting phenomena distinct from both classical gravastars and black holes. We analyze static, spherically symmetric solutions and explore the scalar field's influence on the internal structure and external spacetime geometry. Through perturbative analysis, we identify stability regimes and conditions under which scalarized configurations are favored energetically. Astrophysically, scalarized gravastars may produce signatures in gravitational waveforms distinct from those of classical black holes, particularly during mergers or ringdown phases. In light of current and upcoming data from LIGO-Virgo-KAGRA and the Event Horizon Telescope, scalarized gravastars present an intriguing testbed for modified gravity and quantum gravity phenomenology. Our findings suggest that future multi-messenger observations may be capable of distinguishing scalarized gravastars from black holes, providing critical insights into the true nature of compact objects and the validity of Einstein's theory in strong-field regimes.

Keywords: modified gravity, scalar field, gravastars

*Speaker

Simulation of Proton Decay Using the PHAST Code System in the Hyper-Kamiokande Experiment

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Within the framework of Grand Unified Theories (GUTs), proton decay is predicted to occur through various hypothetical channels, in contrast to the Standard Model (SM) of particle physics, which assumes proton stability. This contribution presents simulation results for proton decay within the context of the Japanese Hyper-Kamiokande experiment, focusing on the proton \rightarrow positron + π decay channel, widely regarded as a key signature in many GUT variants. We employed the PHAST (Particle Hard and Soft Transport) code system to model particle transport and interactions. The Hyper-Kamiokande detector, a large-scale ultrapure water tank, enables the detection of Cherenkov light produced by relativistic particles, such as positrons and photons from π decay, which manifest as distinct Cherenkov rings on the detector's ultra-sensitive photomultiplier tubes (PMTs). Specifically, the proton \rightarrow positron + π decay produces three Cherenkov rings: one from the positron and two from the photons resulting from π decay. We introduce a novel algorithm developed to identify and separate these rings, enabling accurate reconstruction of the invariant mass. This presentation will provide detailed insights into the simulation methodology, the ring identification algorithm, and the analysis techniques, offering a comprehensive discussion of their implications for proton decay searches in Hyper-Kamiokande.

Keywords: Proton decay, particle transport, Cherenkov radiation, Hyperkamiokande

*Speaker

Commercial Fe powder Testing Using Positron Annihilation Spectroscopy experiments

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A conventional Positron Annihilation Lifetime Spectrometer (PALS), along with Doppler Broadening Spectroscopy (DBS), was assembled and used to perform measurements on iron powder at CRNA's Positron Laboratory. This technique is of particular interest because it is a non-destructive nuclear analysis method, and serve as an effective probe for the microstructural features of matter and defects in material. Both PALS and DBS were tested and optimized, achieving an instrumental resolution (FWHM) for best analysis results. These techniques can be used simultaneously for measurements with PALS consists of a BC418 scintillation detector, R329-02 photomultiplier tube, and analog pulse shaping and timing electronics equipment to perform timing analysis on the detected radiation, while a High Purity Germanium (HPGe) detector is used to measure the energy of positron annihilation photons and record the 0.511 MeV peak spectrum in DBS. The iron powders analyzed were biochemopharma commercial Fe (metal) powder with 99.5% purity, poured into a holder to form a structure called a "sandwich source". The results obtained for each measured spectrum of PALS contained approximately at least 10^6 counts. Positron lifetimes results were obtained for Fe powder $\tau = 0.2342 \pm 0.0045$ ns, where the measurements of line parameters of broadened 0.511 MeV peak were $S = 0.49263 \pm 0.00120$ and $W = 0.007108 \pm 0.000167$. The measured positron lifetime suggests a high density of defects, such as vacancies or dislocations since the metal is of powder form, while The S-parameter represents the fraction of low-momentum electrons contributing to the annihilation process, which is sensitive to open volume defects, indicating a larger volume fraction of such defects. The W-parameter gives information about the high-momentum part of the electron momentum distribution, related to the chemical environment of the defects. The combination of PALS and DBS provides comprehensive insights into the defect structure of materials. The results for the iron powder reveal a significant presence of defects, highlighting the effectiveness of these methods in probing and quantifying microstructural anomalies. These findings have important implications for understanding the properties and behaviors of powdered metal materials, which can impact their processing and application in various industries.

Keywords: positron annihilation lifetime spectroscopy, Doppler Broadening Spectroscopy, Positron

*Speaker

annihilation Lifetime, Na, 22 Positron source, Nuclear techniques, Iron Powder.

Formulation and Validation of a Semi-Empirical Model Using Experimental and Evaluated Data

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A new semi-empirical formula was developed to calculate (n, d) cross sections at 14–15 MeV. The Droplet Model (Myers & Swiatecki) was used to describe the reaction energy. The compound nucleus formalism within the evaporation model was applied to derive the formula. Terms contributing to $Q(n, d)$ were analysed and the most relevant ones selected.

Experimental data from the EXFOR database were fitted to determine free parameters.

Systematic trends of (n, d) reactions were investigated.

Predictions were compared with existing models and evaluated libraries (e.g., TENDL). Results show a more accurate description of (n, d) cross sections than previous formulas.

Keywords: cross section, evaporation, energy, systematic, Exfor.

*Speaker

Investigation of ^{129}I Transmutation Process in BR2 Reactor

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Iodine-129 constitutes one of the main long-lived fission products contributing significantly to the radiological risk of nuclear waste. With a radioactive half-life of 1.57×10^7 years, this radioisotope represents a major challenge for sustainable management of high-level radioactive waste. Transmutation by neutron capture offers a promising pathway to convert ^{129}I into stable ^{136}Xe , thereby reducing the long-term radiotoxicity of nuclear waste.

This study numerically evaluates the transmutation rate of iodine-129 in the high-flux BR2 reactor using the ChainSolver 2.34 calculation code. The methodological approach consists of simulating the irradiation of iodine-129 targets in two distinct irradiation positions of the BR2 reactor: the central position H1 and position A/B. The calculations are performed for two different irradiation periods of 193 and 271 days, corresponding to the experimental conditions of the EFTTRA-T1 and PROJECT-1 programs.

The simulations reveal significant transmutation rates: 17.26% and 23.38% for position H1, and 11.38% and 15.62% for position A/B, respectively for 193 and 271 days of irradiation. These results considerably exceed the experimental rates obtained in the HFR reactor at Petten, which reach 5% for EFTTRA-T1 and 3.6-3.9% for PROJECT-1.

The comparative analysis demonstrates that the high epithermal and fast neutron fluxes of BR2 favor the transmutation of ^{129}I compared to thermal spectra. This study confirms the potential of the BR2 reactor as an efficient facility for transmutation of long-lived fission products and contributes to the optimization of nuclear waste management strategies through transmutation.

Keywords: Iodine, 129, Nuclear transmutation, BR2 reactor, Fission products, ChainSolver code, Nuclear waste management

*Speaker

Effects of Lee-Huang-Yang quantum and thermal corrections on Anderson localization.

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We investigate, both analytically and numerically, the effects of Lee-Huang-Yang quantum and thermal corrections on Anderson localization in binary Bose mixtures subjected to correlated disordered potentials. We calculate the localization length and show that, for one-dimensional speckle potentials, the peculiar interplay between disorder and Lee-Huang-Yang fluctuations can enhance localization in one component while inducing delocalization in the other. Our results also reveal that thermal fluctuations lead to the emergence of two or multiple localization maxima.

Keywords: LHY fluctuations, thermal corrections, disordered potentials, Anderson localization, binary Bose mixtures .

*Speaker

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Does the Synchrotron External Forward Shock Model fit multiband of Gamma-Ray Burst afterglow light curves?

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The XRT and UVOT telescopes aboard the Swift Gamma-Ray Burst satellite have provided us with exceptionally high-quality X-ray and optical afterglow data for Gamma-Ray Bursts (GRBs). This presents an intriguing opportunity to evaluate the effectiveness of the external forward shock model in providing a unified fit for both X-ray and optical observational data across a specific selection of GRB afterglows. To pursue this goal, we conducted numerical calculations to simulate the dynamic evolution of the fireball synchrotron model, generating corresponding theoretical light curves. We employed a Monte-Carlo multiband fitting analysis tool, utilizing the χ^2 minimization approach, to compare these theoretical light curves with the observed data. The results of the fitting process and the correlations among various physical parameters are presented and extensively discussed.

Keywords: GRBs, Afterglows, Light curves, Swift

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Probing Binary Neutron Star Mergers and Collisions with a New SPH Code System

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In this contribution, we present the first results obtained with our new C++ SPH (Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics) code, specifically developed to simulate mergers and collisions of compact stars. This initial study focuses on the hydrodynamical evolution of binary neutron star systems, under the assumption of non-rotating and non-magnetized components. In a second phase, we analyze the dynamics within the orbital plane with the goal of constraining key binary parameters such as mass ratio, impact parameter, and relative velocity and evaluating whether these systems can give rise to GRB-like accretion disks. Such disks could in turn lead to the production of relativistic ejecta capable of generating GRB flashes. The results are presented in terms of SPH density fields in the orbital plane, computed using an adaptive mesh refinement (AMR) algorithm. Further details and discussion are provided in this poster.

Keywords: Binary Neutron Stars, Smoothed particle hydrodynamics, Accretion Discs

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Structural, Electronic, and Thermoelectric Properties of FeNiMnSi Heusler Alloys: A First-Principles Approach

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In this work, we studied the structural, electronic and thermoelectric properties of FeNiMnSi Heusler alloys under Hydrostatic pressure using the pseudo-potential plane wave method in the framework of the density functional theory (DFT). The calculations were performed by using the ultra-soft pseudo-potential plane wave (PP-PW) method within generalized gradient (GGA-PBE) as implemented in the CASTEP code.

The structural optimization showed that FeNiMnSi Heusler compound is chemically stable and crystallize in the ferromagnetic YI-type structure. The electronic bands structure analysis under pressure indicated that the FeNiMnSi Heusler compound maintains a metallic behavior throughout the considered pressure range from 0 to 77.5 GPa.

The thermoelectric properties of the FeNiMnSi Heusler compound were calculated such as: the variations of the electrical transport coefficients, including Seebeck coefficient (S), electrical conductivity (σ), electronic thermal conductivity (κ_e), power factor (PF), and figure of merit (ZT) as functions of temperature in the (300; 1200) K range at given fixed pressures: P = 0 GPa, 22.34 GPa, 45.85 GPa, and 77.46 GPa, and chemical potential (μ) at the fermi level (EF), were explored using the semi classical Boltzmann theory within the constant charge carrier relaxation time and rigid band approximations.

Thermoelectric evaluation revealed a relatively high lattice thermal conductivity ($\kappa_l > 1$) and a very low dimensionless figure of merit (ZT)

Keywords: DFT, electronic properties, thermoelectric properties, Heusler compound

*Speaker

Computational and Spectroscopic Insights into the Structural, Electronic, and Nonlinear Optical Properties of 2-NPOB for Energy Applications

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Abstract :

This study investigates the structural, electronic, and nonlinear optical (NLO) properties of 2-nitrophenyl-4-(octyloxy) benzoate (2-NPOB) to assess its potential for energy and optoelectronic applications. The molecular geometry was optimized using density functional theory (DFT), providing insights into torsion angles, bond lengths, and conformational behavior. Simulated FT-IR and ¹H/¹³C NMR spectra validated the vibrational and electronic features, while UV-Visible calculations identified the main electronic transitions. Molecular electrostatic potential (MEP) mapping highlighted reactive sites, confirming regions of electrophilic and nucleophilic activity. In addition, the computed dipole moment, polarizability, and first hyperpolarizability values demonstrated a strong NLO response. These results show how combining theoretical modeling with spectroscopic characterization can support the design of functional molecules. Overall, 2-NPOB emerges as a promising candidate for advanced optoelectronic and sustainable energy technologies.

Keywords: 2 NPOB, DFT, FT IR, MEP, NLO.

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Montmorillonite clay/alginate beads for malachite green adsorption

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The release of dyes into aquatic environments is a serious environmental and health problem in recent years. Therefore, the development of potential adsorbents for the effective removal of malachite green (MG) of aqueous media is of great importance. In this study, new alginate beads were successfully prepared by encapsulation of montmorillonite (Na-Mt) and Nickel oxide modified montmorillonite (NiO-Mt) in alginate using CaCl₂ solution (Alg/Na-Mt and Alg/NiO-Mt). The obtained beads were utilized as a well adsorbents for the removal of MG dye from aqueous solutions by batch adsorption procedure. The characteristics of the synthesized beads were investigated using FTIR and pHPZC. The effects of various operation factors such as contact time, dye initial concentration and temperature on the removal of MG were studied. Moreover, adsorption isotherm results showed that the Freundlich model fitted well for the adsorption of MG onto Alg/Na-Mt and Alg/NiO-Mt beads. Kinetic and thermodynamic studies also indicated that the MG adsorption were found to be well fitted with a pseudo-second-order kinetic model, feasible, endothermic, and spontaneous in nature. In addition, the Alg/Na-Mt and Alg/NiO-Mt beads showed excellent reusability for the removal of the dye after seven adsorption cycles. Overall, the obtained results suggest that Alg/Na-Mt and Alg/NiO-Mt beads could be considered as a low-cost and eco-friendly adsorbents for dye contaminants removal from aquatic media.

Keywords: Alginate, Montmorillonite, NiO, beads, Malachite green

*Speaker

Synthesis and Characterization of Novel Alginate-Marl Clay Beads for Oxytetracycline Removal

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The contamination of wastewater and surface waters by micro-contaminants is a significant environmental issue globally. These contaminants, which include pharmaceuticals, personal care products, industrial chemicals, and pesticides, exhibit notable stability and resistance to degradation, complicating their effective removal in sewage treatment facilities. Over 600 active pharmaceutical compounds have been detected in surface waters worldwide, including drinking water sources. These substances persist even after the treatment of municipal wastewater. Particularly concerning are antibiotics, which continuously infiltrate aquatic systems. Human excretion into urban wastewater systems is the primary source of this contamination with additional contributions from veterinary use, agriculture, and the pharmaceutical industry. The release of antibiotic drugs into aquatic environments is a serious environmental and health problem in recent years, and the removal of these compounds from the water bodies can be quite challenging in the field of wastewater treatment. Therefore, the development of potential adsorbents for the effective removal of oxytetracycline (OTC) from aqueous solution via adsorption technique using the low-cost structured alginate cross linked beads which can be easily recovered after the process is of great importance.

This study successfully developed novel alginate beads (Alg@M) by encapsulating natural marl clay within a sodium alginate matrix, crosslinked with Ca^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , or Fe^{3+} ions. The beads were characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), and their physical properties including moisture content, size, density, and point of zero charge (pHpzc) were analyzed. The primary application investigated was the adsorption of the antibiotic oxytetracycline hydrochloride (OTC) from water. In batch tests, the beads demonstrated exceptional removal efficiency exceeding 96% under optimal conditions: 90 minutes of contact time, 0.5 g of bead mass, a pH of 4.33, an agitation speed of 100 rpm, and an initial OTC concentration of 50 mg/L.

Keywords: Keywords: Alginate, marl clay, synthesis, characterization, antibiotic, removal.

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Synthesis and Characterization of Biopolymer-Based Zeolite Hydrogel Beads

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Significant research interest has recently focused on surface adsorption for eliminating organic pollutants from industrial effluent. Hydrogels represent a promising class of adsorbents owing to their straightforward synthesis, facile separation, and practical applicability. In this study, a new biopolymer-based zeolite hydrogel beads was prepared via a simple chemical cross-linking method. The obtained biopolymer was characterized by the point of zero charge (pHpzc), XRD, FTIR, and SEM/EDX, and then tested as an adsorbent for the removal of a cationic dye from an aqueous solution. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis confirmed the crystalline structure of the zeolite powder. The XRD pattern of the composite hydrogel beads, however, reveals an amorphous structure, due to the encapsulation of the zeolite within the polymer. The adsorption isotherms were modeled using the Langmuir, Temkin, and the Freundlich isotherm equations. The equilibrium adsorption data were described by the Langmuir isotherm model, suggesting a monolayer adsorption process. The kinetic study was best described by the pseudo-second-order kinetic model ($R^2 = 0.999$). Consequently, these results indicate that the biopolymer-based zeolite beads are an efficient, inexpensive, and eco-friendly adsorbent for removing cationic dyes from wastewater.

Keywords: Zeolite, Hydrogels, Dye, Removal, Kinetics study, Isotherm.

*Speaker

Stability and Physical Properties of Alloys Based on Rh, Ir, Pd, and Pt

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In this work, we conducted a comprehensive theoretical study of the structural, electronic, and elastic properties of binary transition-metal alloys based on Rh, Ir, Pd, and Pt, using *ab initio* DFT calculations (GGA-PBE). The results reveal that the Rh–Ir, Pd–Pt, and Rh–Pt alloys exhibit remarkable crystalline stability. Among them, PdPt is the most thermodynamically stable, with a formation enthalpy of -35.73 meV/atom, reflecting strong Pd–Pt bonding. Electronic structure analysis (TDOS, PDOS, and band structures) confirms the metallic character of these alloys, with distinct orbital contributions depending on composition. Elastic property calculations show that Rh- and Ir-based alloys possess the highest elastic constants ($C \approx 442$ – 550 GPa and $C \approx 193$ – 207 GPa), indicating exceptional resistance to uniaxial compression and shear deformation. Furthermore, the low elastic anisotropy coefficients of Rh–Ir (1.33–1.56) and Rh–Pt (1.66–1.73) highlight their near-isotropic mechanical behavior.

Keywords: Rhodium, Iridium, Palladium, Platine, CASTEP, GGA, DFT

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STRUCTURAL AND MECHANISTIC CHARACTERIZATION OF DUAL CATION CROSS-LINKED ALGINATE-KAOLIN COMPOSITE BEADS FOR ADVANCED ADSORPTIVE APPLICATIONS

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This study presents a comprehensive characterization of dual cation cross-linked alginate-kaolin hydrogel beads (Fe/Ca-Alg@K) developed for chlortetracycline (CTC) adsorption. Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) analysis identified characteristic functional groups from both alginate (O-H stretching at 3410 cm⁻¹, carboxylate vibrations at 1620/1427 cm⁻¹) and kaolin (O-H stretches at 3626/3487 cm⁻¹, Si-O-Si vibration at 1034 cm⁻¹, Al-OH deformation at 934 cm⁻¹). X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns confirmed the preservation of kaolinite crystalline structure with characteristic peaks at 12.36° and 24.86°, while reduced peak intensity indicated homogeneous distribution within the alginate matrix. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) imaging demonstrated the transformation from kaolin's irregular crystalline morphology (0.2 μm particles) to spherical composite beads (1-1.5 mm) featuring irregular, porous surfaces with cracks and folds that enhanced specific surface area. Post-adsorption characterization revealed surface deposition of fine particles in SEM images and band shifts in FT-IR spectra, confirming successful CTC uptake. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis showed binding energy shifts for Ca 2p, Si 2p, and Fe 2p peaks, indicating multiple adsorption mechanisms including cation-π interactions, hydrogen bonding, and complexation. This study showed that the beads effectively adsorbed CTC where an optimal dosage of 200 mg of beads achieved a notable removal rate of 95.12% at an initial CTC concentration of 50 mg/L. Moreover, these beads have the potential to reduce chemical oxygen demand (COD) to acceptable levels in pharmaceutical and surface wastewaters.

Keywords: Alginate, Kaolin, Characterization, X, ray photoelectron spectroscopy, X, ray diffraction, Scanning electron microscopy, Adsorption.

*Speaker

Structural and Dipole Moment Variations upon Excitation in Organic Dyes for DSSCs: A DFT and TD-DFT Investigation

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Dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs) rely on the optical and electronic properties of their sensitizing dyes. In particular, the structural and dipole moment changes that occur upon electronic excitation can significantly influence charge injection and separation at the dye–semiconductor interface.

In this work, we investigate a series of organic donor– π –acceptor dyes using Density Functional Theory (DFT) and Time-Dependent DFT (TD-DFT). Ground-state geometries and dipole moments were obtained through DFT optimizations. TD-DFT calculations were then used to identify the most optically active excited states, based on oscillator strength, which served as the basis for excited-state geometry optimizations.

We analyzed and compared the dipole moments in both ground and excited optimized structures to assess how photoexcitation alters charge distribution. Structural changes between the two states were also evaluated to identify any geometry relaxation effects relevant to dye performance.

This computational approach offers a detailed view of how electronic excitation impacts both molecular structure and polarity. These insights are essential for understanding dye behavior in DSSCs and for guiding the design of next-generation sensitizers with improved photovoltaic performance.

Keywords: DSSCs, organic dyes, dipole moment, GSOP, ESOP, TD, DFT

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Computational Determination of Structural, Electromagnetic, and Phonon Stability Properties in a Double Perovskite Ferroelectric Compound

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*Double perovskite materials are particularly well suited for energy applications because of their nontoxic, efficient, and environmentally advantageous characteristics. Using the full-potential linearized augmented-plane-wave approach, Ba₂DyTaO₆ oxide double perovskite was thoroughly examined to investigate the microstructural, magnetic, and optoelectronic properties. The thermodynamic and structural stability was mapped by computing the phonon properties, tolerance factor, and octahedral factor, respectively, which revealed that Ba₂DyTaO₆ was highly stable. The results were determined based on the electronic and magnetic properties obtained from the data. The band edges at the same symmetry points indicated that there was a direct bandgap in the (*V*–*C*) direction in the majority spin, a value equal to 3.793 eV with an overlap in the minority spin. With an integer magnetic moment value of 5.00 μ_B , the Ba₂DyTaO₆ compound exhibits half-metallic and ferromagnetic behavior. This research is the first of its kind in terms of optical properties. It can be concluded that the Ba₂DyTaO₆ material has high absorption, and can be applied in future optoelectronic applications throughout a wide energy range of the light spectrum. Given the limited availability of theoretical and experimental data, the present investigation can provide value for future studies on this compound. Our findings can thus pave the way for additional investigations into the potential use of this oxide material in numerous chemical and physical applications intended for socioeconomic needs.*

Keywords: Ba₂DyTaO₆, Ferroelectric Compound, Elasto, Mechanical Stability, Structural and Electromagnetic Properties

*Speaker

CHARACTERIZATION OF SYNTHETIC SiO₂ FOR DOSIMETRY PURPOSES

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Quartz (SiO₂) is a widely studied material in dosimetry due to its sensitivity to ionizing radiation, its abundance in nature and low cost (1). For this purpose, SiO₂ was synthesized via the sol-gel process at our laboratory using well-determined amounts of reagents to achieve properties that closely match those of natural quartz but with higher purity. Thermoluminescence (TL) and Continuous Wave Optically Stimulated Luminescence (CW-OSL) measurements were performed using the Risø TL/OSL reader DA-20 model. Key dosimetric aspects such as dose-response behavior, combination of TL and OSL reading modes and kinetic parameters were investigated over a wide range of doses varying from 0.1 Gy to 100 Gy. The kinetic parameters obtained from the deconvolution of TL and CW-OSL curves were performed using algorithms developed and implemented in Python based on the mathematical frame-work of general order. The results reveal a strong linearity in the studied dose region. The combination of TL and OSL reading modes study shows a decrease in the intensity of both experimental peaks, yielding a contribution of both optical sensitive traps and thermal traps in the luminescence emission. TL and OSL kinetic parameters were found to range from 0.42 eV to 1.86 eV and 6.02×10^{-20} cm² to 1.21×10^{-18} cm², respectively, which is consistent with the results reported in the literature (2-3). These findings provide valuable insights into the potential use of synthetic quartz as a promising material for radiation detection and dosimetry measurements.

Keywords: TL, OSL, Sol, Gel, SiO₂, Radiation dosimetry, Python

*Speaker

Accumulative Roll Bonding (ARB) and Cross Accumulative Roll Bonding (CARB) of AA1050 alloy

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Accumulative Roll Bonding (ARB) and Cross Accumulative Roll Bonding (CARB) are the most efficient ways to produce bulk Ultrafine-Grained Materials among severe plastic deformation techniques. The goal of such hyper deformation is to achieve metallic samples with superior physical and metallurgical properties. High dislocation density levels as well as substantial grain refinement are prerequisites and can be assured after a certain number of ARB and CARB cycles. During this work, a comparison of both techniques was achieved through the evolutions of the dislocation density and microhardness on a commercial AA1050 alloy as a function of strain. The attempts were successful and six ARB and CARB cycles were effectively realized without neither considerable cracking of the sample surface nor bending. The results show that in the case of CARB, the evolution of microhardness is greater than in ARB. Evolution in dislocation density after severe plastic deformation (ARB and CARB) was achieved, the dislocation density increased seems to have reached a saturated value after the 3rd cycle for both processing.

Keywords: Severe Plastic Deformation, ARB, CARB, AA1050 alloy, dislocation, microhardness.

*Speaker

Ab initio study of porosity effect on elastic properties of porous silicon

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In this work, the effect of porosity on the elastic properties of porous silicon (PSi) was investigated using the ab-initio pseudo potential plane wave (PP-PW) approach based on density functional theory (DFT). The elastic properties of PSi, such as elastic constants, the bulk modulus, the shear modulus, the Young's modulus and the Poisson's ratio as a function of different porosities, are determined by using supercell model and compared to those published in the literature. The results show that The Young's E modulus decreases by increasing the porosity, between 124 GPa (for bulk Si) and 32 GPa (for porosity of 40%), thus indicating a decreasing in the rigidity of PSi for higher porosity. In contrast, the shear modulus G values of PSi are lower than that of bulk modulus B for the four porosities so the porous material is more resistive to compression than to shear. A comparison between the elastic properties of porous silicon determined by DFT and those obtained experimentally collected from the literature are in good agreement and show similar behavior. Hence, our model yields good outcomes.

Keywords: porous silicon, DFT, supercell model, Young's modulus

*Speaker

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Analysis of Vibration and Buckling Characteristics of Porous Functionally Graded Beams on Variable Elastic Foundations Using Higher-Order Shear Deformation Theory

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This study presents an analytical method to investigate the free vibration and stability of both perfect and imperfect functionally graded (FG) beams resting on variable elastic foundations (VEFs), employing a three-variable higher-order shear deformation theory (HSDT). Unlike conventional HSDTs that typically require four unknowns, the proposed approach simplifies the formulation by using only three unknown functions. Moreover, the theory inherently satisfies the boundary condition of zero normal stress on the beam surfaces and accurately captures the hyperbolic distribution of transverse shear stresses without the need for shear correction factors. The elastic foundation is modeled using a two-parameter Winkler–Pasternak formulation, where the Winkler modulus varies along the beam’s length (following linear, parabolic, sinusoidal, cosine, exponential, or uniform distributions), while the Pasternak parameter remains constant. The FG beam’s material properties are assumed to vary through the thickness according to a power-law distribution. To capture the influence of material defects, four different porosity distribution patterns are considered. The governing equations are derived using Hamilton’s principle and solved analytically via Navier’s method for simply supported beams. Validation of the proposed model is carried out through comparisons with results from existing literature. Finally, a series of parametric studies are performed to explore the effects of various parameters on the vibration and buckling behavior of FG beams. The proposed theory proves to be both accurate and efficient in predicting the dynamic and stability responses of FG beams on variable elastic foundations.

Keywords: free vibration, FG beam, buckling, elastic foundation.

*Speaker

RhTeI Monolayer: A Multifunctional 2D Material for Photocatalytic Water Splitting and High-Speed Electronics

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Two-dimensional materials, owing to their unique properties, are increasingly investigated for sustainable energy applications such as photocatalysis. In this study, first-principles calculations using the Quantum ESPRESSO software are employed to explore the electronic structure, carrier transport, and photocatalytic performance of the RhTeI monolayer. The results demonstrate that the monolayer is energetically, mechanically, and dynamically stable. The inclusion of spin-orbit coupling (SOC) reduces the band gap from 1.0513 eV (PBEsol) to 0.8071 eV, whereas the hybrid HSE06 functional predicts a value of 1.9598 eV. The RhTeI monolayer exhibits pronounced anisotropy in carrier mobility, with electron mobilities of $345.870 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ along the x-direction and $810.719 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ along the y-direction, reflecting excellent electron transport properties and potential for next-generation high-speed electronic devices. In addition, the band edge positions derived from HSE06 at $\text{pH} = 0$ straddle the water redox potentials, demonstrating the material's potential for photocatalytic water splitting. The RhTeI monolayer is identified as a highly promising photocatalyst, as its predicted solar to hydrogen efficiency (STH) of 15.22% exceeds the 10% criterion for commercial hydrogen generation.

Keywords: RhTeI monolayer, First, principles calculations, Quantum ESPRESSO, Electronic properties, Carrier mobility, Solar to hydrogen efficiency

*Speaker

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Commercial bentonite nanomaterial: composition, structure and textural characterization

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The physic and chemical characterization of the commercial bentonite from the Biochem Chemopharma company (France) shows that it is mainly constituted by sodium montmorillonite due to its Na⁺ content. The material has a specific surface area of 76.97 m²/g, a pore volume of about 1.15 cm³/g, and both N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms exhibit a hysteresis loop of H3 type. The thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of the studied mineral presents the first endothermic peak, characteristic of montmorillonite, in 110 °C that corresponds to the loss of water, and can be extended up to 250 °C. The Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) spectra shows the existence of Si-OH, Al-Al-OH and Si-O-Si functional groups in clay sample. The X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns and relative basal spacing show that the major peaks correspond to montmorillonite and the d₀₀₁ value of the basal bentonite peak (12.55 Å) suggests that the main interlayer cation is sodium.

Keywords: Commercial bentonite, Characterization, TGA, FTIR, XRD

*Speaker

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First principles study of ZnO doped with Co and Ni: structure, electronic and elastic properties

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This work presents a comprehensive *ab initio* investigation of the structural, electronic, and elastic properties of Co, Ni co-doped zinc oxide within the DFT+ U framework. A realistic $2\times 2\times 2$ wurtzite ZnO supercell is employed to model substitutional doping at controlled Co and Ni concentrations up to 12.5%, sampling representative dopant configurations and separations. Geometry optimizations reveal that co-doping induces local lattice distortions confined to the first cation anion shells while preserving the global wurtzite symmetry. Electronic band-structure and density of states analyses show that the transition metal 3d states hybridize with O(2p)/Zn(4s) manifolds, enabling systematic band-gap tuning as a function of the Co/Ni ratio and total dopant content. The Hubbard U correction is used to capture the localization of 3d electrons and to mitigate the self-interaction error, yielding more reliable gap and state placements. From the computed elastic constants, we verify Born mechanical stability across all compositions and quantify trends in bulk, shear, and Young's moduli, along with elastic anisotropy and ductility indicators, which vary moderately with dopant loading. Overall, the results provide quantitative guidelines for engineering the electronic gap and mechanical response of Co-Ni co-doped ZnO, informing the design of oxide-based optoelectronic and piezoelectric devices.

Keywords: GGA+ U , ZnO:(Ni, Co), Gap energy, supercell

*Speaker

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Impact of a Zinc Sulfide Insulation Layer on CIGS Solar Cell Efficiency

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In this paper, we present a simulation of a CIGS solar cell with a ZnS buffer layer, performed using the Silvaco-Atlas simulator. However, we obtained an efficiency of 24.13%, short-circuit current of 37.81 mA/cm², an open circuit voltage of 740 mV, and a fill factor of 78.78% at a bandgap of 1.41 eV, corresponding to an x ratio of 0.5 for the CIGS solar cell using a ZnS buffer layer. We optimized the performance of the ZnS/CIGS solar cell with the improved effects of layer parameters such as thickness and acceptor densities ZnS buffer layers.

Keywords: Buffer layer (ZnS), CIGS, Solar cell, Optimization, Silvaco, Atlas

*Speaker

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Artificial Intelligence in Nuclear Data Evaluation: Advances and Perspectives for Neutron Cross Sections

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Reliable nuclear reaction cross sections are very important for reactor design, isotope production, and waste transmutation. Normally, these data obtained from experiments and theoretical models. Nevertheless, experiments are expensive and sometimes give incomplete results. Artificial intelligence (AI) can help by giving predictive models that complete missing data and reduce uncertainties. In this work, I present my studies on the evaluation of (n,α) , $(n,2n)$, (n,p) , and (p,n) reaction cross sections. The method uses available experimental data together with AI-based models to reproduce excitation functions and improve the quality of the results. Machine learning tools trained with both experimental and calculated data, and then used to build continuous and more accurate cross-section curves. The results show that AI can support traditional methods by giving better agreement with experiments and predictions that are more reliable in energy regions where measurements are missing. This work highlights the important role of AI in future nuclear data evaluation strategies and in the development of improved nuclear data libraries.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Nuclear Data, Cross Section Evaluation, Machine Learning, Reaction Channels, Excitation Functions

*Speaker

AI-Assisted MRI Image Segmentation: Computational Perspectives in Medical Physics

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Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) plays a central role in neuro-oncology, yet accurate tumor segmentation remains challenging due to anatomical variability and the limitations of manual delineation. This study evaluates the contribution of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to brain MRI segmentation, comparing a classical thresholding method (Otsu) with a deep learning approach.

We employed the LGG-MRI Kaggle dataset (3929 annotated images) and applied standard pre-processing (resizing, normalization, binarization). Two segmentation strategies were compared: Otsu thresholding, representing a simple traditional approach, and a U-Net convolutional neural network (CNN) optimized for biomedical image segmentation.

A quantitative evaluation demonstrated a clear advantage of U-Net: it achieved an Intersection over Union (IoU) of 0.87 and a Dice similarity coefficient of 0.93, compared to 0.46 and 0.61 for Otsu. Visual comparisons further confirmed the superiority of the deep learning method, producing more precise and less noisy delineations of tumor regions.

These findings highlight the transformative role of AI in medical imaging, offering faster, more reliable, and clinically relevant tools for image-guided diagnosis and treatment planning. Moreover, they emphasize the importance of AI-assisted segmentation in medical physics research and practice, providing accurate tools for radiotherapy planning, treatment optimization, and clinical decision support.

Keywords: MRI, Brain tumor, Segmentation, Artificial Intelligence, Deep Learning, U, Net, Medical Physics, Radiotherapy, Clinical decision support

*Speaker

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Study of Structural, Optoelectronic and Photovoltaic Performance of Cu₂SnS₃Compound: Combined DFT and SCAPS-1D Simulations.

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In this paper we have employed the structural and optoelectronic properties and their effectiveness in photovoltaic applications of copper-based ternary semiconductors present in the CuSnS compound. Since there is a significant difference in previous studies regarding the value of the band gaps (0.65-1.35 eV), in an attempt to find the appropriate approximation to study this type of compound. The structural properties were studied by using the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) of Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) and the local density approximation (LDA). Given the important influence that Cu d-electrons play in determining their electronic properties, as shown by the results obtained when using different exchange correlation energy functionals. The combined function of the Becke-Johnson potential modified by Tran and Blaha and the Hubbard potential (TB-mBJ+U) was employed to optimize the calculated anion displacement systematically.

The calculations gave the value of the band gaps. The semiconductor quasiparticle is 0.7 eV in the monoclinic structure (m-CTS; SG: Cc), and that of the orthorhombic structure (gold-CTS; SG: Imm2) is 0.73 eV, which is largely consistent with experimental values.

The study of optical properties such as the dielectric function also revealed the reflectance absorption coefficient and refractive index of the CuSnS compound in its two phases. The latter is considered a promising candidate in optoelectronic applications. To verify this, we used the SCAPS program, and the results were good. When using this compound as an absorbent layer in a photovoltaic cell, the current density J_{sc} increases, reaching its peak at a thickness of 800 nm.

Keywords: Cu₂SnS₃, FP, LAPW, LDA, TB, mBJ+U, photovoltaic cells.

*Speaker

AI for Brain Tumor Classification and Radiotherapy Dose Estimation

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Brain tumor diagnosis and treatment planning rely heavily on the accurate identification of tumor type and characteristics. Manual classification of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) scans is both time-consuming and subject to inter-observer variability, highlighting the need for automated, reproducible solutions.

In this work, we developed an intelligent pipeline based on a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) for the automatic classification of brain tumors and the estimation of therapeutic irradiation doses. The publicly available Kaggle dataset, containing 5,712 brain MRI images across four categories (glioma, meningioma, pituitary adenoma, and no tumor), was used. Images were preprocessed (grayscale conversion, 128×128 resizing, normalization, and CLAHE enhancement), then split into training (80%) and validation (20%) subsets.

The proposed CNN architecture consists of three convolutional–pooling blocks followed by dense layers, totaling ~3.3 million trainable parameters. On the validation set, the model achieved an overall accuracy of 89.6%. Class-wise performance revealed high detection rates for pituitary adenomas (F1-score: 0.94) and non-tumor cases (F1-score: 0.95), while gliomas (F1-score: 0.89) and meningiomas (F1-score: 0.79) showed moderate overlap in visual features, likely due to similarities in MRI slices.

Beyond classification, a complementary function was designed to provide dosimetric estimation. The irradiation dose (in Gy) is adjusted according to tumor type, tumor volume, and proximity to critical structures, thereby simulating a clinical decision-support step in radiotherapy planning. For instance, gliomas near the brainstem received an estimated 55 Gy, while meningiomas close to critical organs were adjusted to ~44 Gy.

This exploratory study demonstrates the feasibility of integrating artificial intelligence into medical physics workflows for both tumor classification and personalized dosimetric support. Although developed in an academic setting with public data, the proposed pipeline offers a solid foundation for future clinical validation, including integration of real patient data, advanced segmentation modules, and potential incorporation into PACS systems for real-time decision support in radiotherapy.

Keywords: Brain tumor classification, Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Radiotherapy dose estimation, Medical physics, Decision support system

*Speaker

Symbolic Framework for the Automated Evaluation of Feynman Diagrams at Finite Temperature

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In this work, we introduce a Python implementation for the automated generation of the analytical contributions of many-body Feynman diagrams at finite temperature. Building on the recently developed finite-temperature many-body perturbation theory (FT-MBPT) and incorporating algorithms from graph theory, the code systematically constructs the analytical expressions of the grand potential for each vacuum diagram, together with the corresponding symmetry factor, at a given perturbative order n . This unified framework not only automates the otherwise cumbersome diagrammatic calculations but also provides a versatile tool for computing the thermodynamic properties of both fermionic and bosonic systems across all temperature regimes, including the zero-temperature limit. Furthermore, the symbolic nature of the implementation ensures transparency, reproducibility, and the potential for extension to more advanced many-body techniques.

Keywords: Finite, temperature many, body perturbation theory, Feynman diagrams, Graph theory, Thermodynamic properties, Symbolic computation

*Speaker

Monte Carlo method

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The Monte Carlo method is an algorithmic technique that makes use of randomness to approximate numerical solutions for complex problems. At its foundation, the method involves generating random variables according to a given probability distribution and then employing these samples to produce statistical estimates of desired values. This reliance on random sampling provides a versatile and powerful framework for addressing a wide variety of problems where analytical or exact solutions are either unavailable. One of the most significant applications of the Monte Carlo method lies in the computation of integrals in high-dimensional spaces. Traditional numerical integration techniques tend to suffer from the "curse of dimensionality," where the number of computations grows exponentially with the number of dimensions. In contrast, Monte Carlo methods remain efficient even in high-dimensional settings because the accuracy of the approximation primarily depends

on the number of samples. In the field of physics, Monte Carlo simulations are essential for modeling and understanding phenomena that involve stochastic behavior or uncertainty. Examples include the study of particle transport, thermodynamic systems, and quantum mechanics. Through repeated random sampling, the method provides insights into physical processes that are difficult to observe directly or to model through deterministic approaches. The Monte Carlo method also plays a central role in finance, particularly in the analysis of risks and uncertainties. It is commonly used in option pricing, portfolio management, and forecasting potential market outcomes under uncertain conditions. By simulating a wide range of possible scenarios, it enables decision-makers to evaluate risks and make informed strategies in an uncertain financial environment. Although highly flexible, the Monte Carlo method is not without limitations. Its accuracy increases with the number of samples, meaning that large-scale simulations often require significant computational resources. Nevertheless, advances in computational power and parallel algorithms have made Monte Carlo simulations increasingly practical for real-world problems.

Overall, the Monte Carlo method has proven itself as a robust, adaptable, and indispensable tool across multiple disciplines, including mathematics, physics, engineering, computer science, and finance. Its ability to approximate solutions in the face of complexity and uncertainty ensures its ongoing importance in both theoretical research and applied domains.

Keywords: Monte Carlo method, random variables, statistical approximation, physical simulation, applied mathematics

*Speaker

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Dust Grain Charging Dynamics in the Presence of Non-Extensive Electrons: Effect of the Density Ratio

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1

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In a dusty plasma, fluctuations of local currents lead to variations in the charge carried by dust grains, making this charge an additional dynamic variable. Moreover, numerous space observations reveal the presence of energetic electrons in various astrophysical environments, and measurements of their distribution function highlight a strongly non-isothermal behavior. Thus, rather than the classical Maxwellian distribution, it is often more relevant, both from a physical and practical standpoint, to employ non-Maxwellian distributions, such as kappa distributions or those derived from nonextensive statistics, to describe plasma kinetics outside thermal equilibrium.

This work focuses on the temporal evolution of dust grain charging in a dusty plasma, with particular emphasis on the influence of electron nonextensivity and on the impact of the density ratio on the charging dynamics. To this end, the adopted approach relies on the numerical solution of the coupled system formed by Poisson's equation and the equation governing the time evolution of the grain charge.

Our results show that the nonextensive parameter plays a crucial role: it not only modifies the equilibrium charge but also affects the transient dynamics of the charging process. In particular, we observe that variations in κ can either accelerate or slow down the establishment of equilibrium, and significantly alter the system's temporal response. These findings therefore highlight the importance of the ion–electron density ratio in providing a realistic description of the dust charging mechanism in complex plasmas.

Keywords: Dusty plasma, Charging process, Tsallis statistics

*Speaker

Raman-Nath Regime: Theoretical Analysis of Diffraction Orders Intensities.

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Abstract: When a sound wave propagates through a transparent medium, it modulates the refractive index via the photoelastic effect, thereby generating a moving phase grating. A Gaussian laser beam interacting with this grating undergoes acousto-optic diffraction, whose characteristics are governed by the Klein-Cook parameter Q , for $Q \ll 1$, the system operates in the Raman-Nath regime, while for $Q \gg 1$, it operates in the Bragg regime. Numerical simulations provide deeper insight into this process. By introducing two frequency-modulated ultrasonic waves propagating orthogonally, with a controlled phase difference between them, the laser beam can be steered along distinct trajectories, including linear, elliptical and circular paths. The distribution of optical intensity among diffraction orders is strongly influenced by the Raman-Nath parameter ($\Psi = 2\pi L \Delta n / \lambda$). At small values of Ψ , most of the optical power remains concentrated in the central order, while at larger values it is redistributed among several higher orders, thereby reducing the central beam intensity.

Keywords: Raman Nath diffraction, Gaussian Laser beam, Diffraction orders intensities, frequency modulation.

*Speaker

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Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy (LIBS) as a Tool for Pesticide Characterization

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Pesticides are among the most significant environmental factors linked to chronic human diseases, including cancer. Their widespread agricultural use for crop protection contributes to the contamination of soil, water, and the broader environment. Many pesticides contain toxic chemicals that pose serious health risks, particularly under prolonged or high-level exposure (Hazrat et al., 2019). Growing evidence also emphasizes the need to study pesticides not only individually but also in combination with other pollutants, such as heavy metals, since such interactions may amplify toxicity and worsen health outcomes (Wallace & Djordjevic, 2020). In parallel, rapid agricultural and industrial development has intensified environmental contamination by heavy metals, including cadmium, lead, copper, and zinc. These elements accumulate in soil through fertilizers, pesticides, and wastewater, are taken up by plants, and subsequently enter the food chain, where they can cause multi-organ toxicity in humans (Paenark et al., 2024; Jaishankar et al., 2014).

This study presents an elemental analysis of four commercially available pesticides-ASTRAD, STORA, STARLIGHT, and FLINT-using Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy (LIBS). The technique proved effective in qualitatively detecting a wide range of elements, including light elements (C, O, N) and toxic heavy metals (Pb, Co, Cu ...). The findings highlight LIBS as a rapid and reliable tool for characterizing pesticides and assessing their potential contribution to environmental and health risks.

Keywords: Heavy Metals, Laser, Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy (LIBS), pesticides, contamination

*Speaker

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Numerical Simulation of Two-Dimensional Lissajous Beam Scanning via Acousto-Optic Deflection

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Acousto-optical deflectors (AODs) are well-known photonic devices used in a number of scientific and industrial applications, providing precise spatial control of light beams via the acousto-optical effect. In this work, we present an advanced approach to steer a Gaussian beam using two perpendicularly arranged AODs, where two frequency-modulated ultrasonic waves propagate within a transparent elastic medium. Under these conditions, the incident Gaussian beam traversing the medium is split into multiple diffracted orders distributed along two dimensions. Each order can be guided along linear, circular, or elliptical trajectories depending on the phase difference between the two acoustic waves. Furthermore, by varying the frequency ratio ω_2/ω_1 , Lissajous trajectories can be generated. The proposed method is validated through numerical simulations, confirming its efficiency for accurate beam steering.

Keywords: Acousto, optical deflectors, diffracted orders, acoustic waves.

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U-Shaped Fiber Optic Sensor for water monitoring

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Fiber optic sensors (FOSs) have garnered considerable attention from researchers worldwide since the development of low-loss fiber optics in the 1970s. FOSs offer some unique benefits compared to conventional sensors (i.e., biological, electrochemical, and semiconductor) in terms of miniaturized size, imperviousness to electromagnetic interference, multiplexing, and remote sensing ability, resilience, lightweight, the ability to sense various physical disturbances such as acoustic, temperature, strain, and pressure, and the inability to conduct electricity, among others. In particular, fiber optics bent into a U-shape presents various advantages over other approaches, and this configuration considerably improves performance in terms of sensitivity. The improvement in sensitivity can be attributed to the enhanced penetration depth of the evanescent field and the increased evanescent power in the cladding or surrounding medium. Consequently, a larger portion of the propagating light experiences changes due to variations in the local refractive index (RI). In this work, we used a U-shaped fiber optic sensor for water quality analysis, explaining the underlying principles. The performance of optical fiber sensors is influenced by multiple factors, including the type of fiber material, stretching technologies, sensitive reagents and materials, coating and chemical synthesis technologies, as well as the performance of the chip and detection system. The development of optimal FOS sensors requires cross-disciplinary integration and collaboration.

Keywords: Optical fiber sensor, Water pollution, Concentration measurement

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Study of the Geiger Müller conter

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The Geiger Müller conter is a radiation detection instrument used to measure ionizing radiation such as alpha, beta particles and gamma rays. It operates by detecting the ionization produced when radiation passes through a low-pressure gaz inside a metal tube. In this lab experiment, we use a GM conter and a radioactive source, our main objectives are to identify the effective operating voltage (threshold voltage), determine the dead time of the detector and study how detected events change with varying distances using source of Cs (137), after completing the experiment on yield variation with source-detector distance, we proceed to study how the detection yield varies with the atomic number z of Betta-emiting sources and their average Betta energy.

Keywords: Geiger Müller conter, the plateau, beta sources, dead time, yield measurement, threshold voltage

*Speaker

Cavitation Phenomenon through Venturi Using Computational Fluid Dynamics: Influence of throat length

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Hydrodynamic cavitation is the damage phenomenon in several industrial applications when the local liquid pressure decreases under the vapor pressure. In this present work, our objective is to investigate the effect of different throat lengths of the venturi on the characteristics of cavitating flow. The computational fluid dynamic (CFD) was selected with a cavitation model. The mixture model for the multiphase flow and K-W SST turbulence model were adopted. The numerical results are compared to the previous experimental and numerical data. The static pressure distribution, fluid velocity and vapor fraction formation are analyzed and discussed. The obtained results demonstrated that the throat length of the venturi has a influence on cavitation phenomenon, when the throat length increases leads to delay pressure recovery. The vapor formation fraction remains consistent with an increase in throat length. For the geometry without a throat, the vapor concentration is observed lower compared to the other throat lengths; $l = 4, 9, 20$ mm. Moreover, the increase in throat length results only in a shift in the onset and location of vapor formation.

Keywords: Hydrodynamic cavitation, venturi, CFD, Vapor.

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Numerical Investigation of Liquid Film Thickness in Slug Flow Trough Horizontal Mini and Micro-Channels

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The thickness of the liquid film between the channel wall and the elongated gas bubble is the focus of this study. A numerical analysis is carried out to investigate the influence of inlet conditions on the film thickness. The volume of fluid (VOF) method is employed as the interface-tracking technique within the open-source CFD platform OpenFOAM.

This study investigates two-phase (air-water) flow in the inlet region of a small horizontal circular tube. Water flows through tubes of varying diameters (3 mm, 1 mm, 0.8 mm and 0.5 mm), while air is injected axially through a nozzle with an inner diameter of 0.11 mm. The governing equations (continuity and momentum) coupled with VOF method, are used to model the physics of the problem.

The results highlight the effects of channel confinement and gas velocity on the film thickness in slug flow within horizontal mini- and micro-channels. At low capillary numbers, inertial effects are shown to be negligible. As the tube diameter decreases, the confinement effects become more pronounced, significantly altering the balance of forces acting on the fluid. Inertial and gravitational forces diminish, while surface tension and viscous forces become increasingly dominant. This shift in the force balance modifies the flow characteristics and alters the liquid-gas interface and shape of the elongated bubbles. Additionally, the confinement effect is found to be more significant at higher gas velocities.

Keywords: Two, phase flow, slug flow, microfluidics, liquid film.

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Evaluation of the Chemical Potential and Boson Number Using Polylogarithmic Methods

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The chemical potential (μ) represents a key thermodynamic variable that defines the state of a system in both classical and quantum regimes. Recent advances have focused on the determination of μ for a free Fermi gas at low temperatures. In this work, we present a solution for the chemical potential in three dimensions by employing the polylogarithm function. Furthermore, the number of bosonic atoms is evaluated using both exact summation and integral methods, and a detailed comparison between these two approaches is provided.

Keywords: Bose Einstein condensate, statistical physics, polylogarithme function, statistical thermodynamic.

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